

**ORGANIZATION FOR HUMAN BRAIN MAPPING (OHBM) ANNUAL
MEETING
JUNE 23-25, 2020**

**LOW FIELD MRI-A POSSIBLE BRAIN IMAGING MODALITY FOR SUB-
SAHARAN AFRICA**

Johnes Obungoloch, Ph.D

MBARARA UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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Mbarara City

Students ~4,200

Johnes Obungoloch, Ph.D

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If MRI were a source of light, Africa would be in darknes and Uganda would be even darker

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MRI distribution in Africa

Table 2: Distribution of MRI Units in the West African Sub-Region (per million)

Country	Population (2017)	MRI Units	(Approx. Per Million Population)	GDP	Human Development Index
*Nigeria	191,835,936	58	0.30	2,929.525	0.514
*Ghana	28,656,723	14	0.48	1,384.354	0.579
Mauritania	4,266,448	3	0.77	1,197.121	0.506
*Ivory Coast	23,815,886	2	0.08	1425.056	0.462
Senegal	16,054,275	2	0.14	945.863	0.466
*Guinea	13,290,659	1	0.07	519.173	0.411
Burkina Faso	19,173,322	1	0.06	644.502	0.402
Togo	7,691,915	1	0.15	586.301	0.484
Gambia	2,120,418	1	0.54	435.452	0.441
Cape Verde	533,468	1	2.00	3,057.916	0.646
Benin Republic	11,458,611	0	0.00	814.360	0.480
Mali	18,689,966	0	0.00	844.274	0.419
Liberia	4,730,437	0	0.00	478.681	0.430
Niger	21,563,607	0	0.00	412.797	0.348
Sierra Leone	6,732,899	0	0.00	635.892	0.413
Guinea Bissau	1,932,871	NA	NA	624.671	0.420
Total		83			

* Information originating from by the current survey

- ❑ Uganda has 4 MRI scanners
- ❑ Population ~ 42.86 Million
- 1 MRI for about 10.7M people

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Early MRI systems were low field, How did Africa lag behind?

Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging

FIGURE 3: Historical photographs and sketches showing one of the first MRI systems to produce human images, together with RF coil and in vivo breast images.

Marques et al, 2019

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Open Access

Research

Survey of magnetic resonance imaging availability in West Africa

Godwin Inaleawu Oobole^{1,A}, Adekunle Olakunle Adevomove², Augustina Badu-Penrah³, Yaw Mensah⁴, Donald Amasike Nzeh⁵

Table 1: Distribution of magnetic resonance imaging machines in Nigeria

State/Region	MRI Units	Government (High Field/Low Field)	Private (High Field /Low Field)
Lagos	14	0/2	5/7
Abuja	10	2/3	3/2
Port Harcourt	6	0/1	0/5
Kano	3	0/0	0/3
Ibadan	2	0/1	0/1
Ilorin	2	0/1	0/1
Zaria	2	0/1	0/1
Enugu	2	0/0	0/2
Jos	2	0/1	0/1
Delta	2	1/0	0/1
Yenagoa	2	0/2	0/0
Maiduguri	1	0/1	0/0
Ile-Ife	1	0/1	0/0
Nnewi	1	0/1	0/0
Bauchi	1	0/1	0/0
Sokoto	1	0/1	0/0
Kaduna	1	0/1	0/0
Gombe	1	0/0	0/1
Umuahia	1	0/0	0/1
Ondo	1	0/0	0/1
Yola	1	0/0	0/1
Calabar	1	0/0	0/1
Total	58	21(3/18)	37(8/29)

Over 80% of the MRI systems are low field -Permanent Magnet

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How did Africa Lag behind?-Advances in MRI Technology/hardware

- Cost
- Technical requirements and expertise
- Infrastructure

While modern MRI systems generate very impressive images, its a luxury in many developing countries

Credit: University at Buffalo

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Requirements for new low field MRI systems-Sustainability

- Local technical expertise need to be developed
- Local Manufacturing capacity
- Inexpensive
- Flexible infrastructure requirements
- Support from clinical personnel
- Low power requirements
- Reduced technical complexity of the devices

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Low field MRI systems for developing countries-Resistive Magnet Systems

Design

Fabrication

Images

Obungoloch et al, 2018

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New resistive coil base mri system under construction at MUST

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Focus-Hydrocephalus

- ❑ **Hydrocephalus** - Accumulation of Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF)
- ❑ **Prevalence** >100,000 children per year
- ❑ **Burden** \$26 - 48B / yr

*Hydrocephalic baby
(Warf et al. 2011).*

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Focus-Hydrocephalus

Credit: cure.org/uganda

- CT is used
- CT – Risks of cancer

(Brenner et al 2007)

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Low-Cost High-Performance MRI

Mathieu Sarraclanie^{1,2}, Cristen D. LaPierre^{1,2}, Najat Salameh^{1,2,3}, David E. J. Waddington^{1,2,4}, Thomas Witzel¹ & Matthew S. Rosen^{1,2,5}

Figure 1. Ultra-low field MRI system. Custom built biplanar 6.5mT electromagnet with biplanar gradients (Gx, Gy, and Gz). The diameter of the outermost B₀ coil is 220cm. The subject lays supine in the scanner and a custom built single channel transmit/receive spiral head coil wound with litz wire for operation at 276 kHz is placed to cradle the head.

Figure 3. 3D images of the living brain acquired in 6 minutes at 6.5mT in (a) axial, (b) coronal, and (c) sagittal orientation. The corresponding maximum SNRs are a. 15, b. 21, and c. 16. Acquisition matrix: 64 × 75 × 15, voxel size: a. (2.5 × 3.5 × 8.5) mm³, b. (2.5 × 3.5 × 11.5) mm³, and c. (2.5 × 3.5 × 14.4) mm³.

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Low field MRI systems -Hallbach Arrays

Small magnets

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Low field MRI systems -Halbach Arrays

In vivo three-dimensional brain and extremity MRI at 50 mT using a permanent magnet Halbach array

T. O'Reilly¹, W. M. Teeuwisse¹, D. de Gans², K.Koolstra¹, A. G. Webb^{1,2}

Figure 7. Images acquired with different weighting at a spatial resolution of $4 \times 4 \times 4$ mm. (a) T1- weighted (2.5 mins data acquisition time), (b) T2-weighted (2 mins) and (c) inversion-recovery TSE sequence (2 mins). (d) Higher resolution image ($2 \times 2 \times 4$ mm) from a different volunteer (13 minutes)

LEIDEN UNIVERSITY
MEDICAL CENTER

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A Dictionary Learning Approach for Noise-Robust Image Reconstruction in Low-Field Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Emmanuel AHISHAKIYE^{1,2}, Martin Bastiaan VAN GIJZEN³, Julius TUMWIINE⁴, Johnes OBUNGOLOCH¹

(b) Image Reconstruction using our proposed algorithm, DLMRI and TBMDU
(i) Using a Phantom Image

Figure 1.3: The original image (a) that was used for reconstruction. The results after 10 iterations for TBMDU, DLMRI and our proposed algorithm were (b), (c) and (d) respectively.

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MRI for Africa - New initiatives

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MRI for Africa -New initiatives

Committee For Advancement of MRI Education and Research in Africa-CAMERA

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MRI for Africa -New initiatives

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Work together to avoid this

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If we don't, we might also end up here

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SUCCEED WE MUST

open source imaging

Open Science Room

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**THANK
YOU**